

Analytical Method Development for Simultaneous Estimation of Quinine and Ciprofloxacin

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Abstract: The simple, accurate, precise, reproducible and economic UV spectroscopic methods of quinine and ciprofloxacin have been developed for the simultaneous estimation. The method A-dual wavelength, method B-area under curve and method C-absorption ratio method were developed by using JASCO double beam UV Spectrophotometer (model-V630). As simultaneous estimation was carried out, measurement of absorbance at two wavelengths 233 nm and 272 nm which shows λ_{\max} values of quinine and ciprofloxacin respectively in distilled water. Quinine and ciprofloxacin shows linearity at selected wavelengths and obeys beers law in the concentration range of 5-30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ with good correlation coefficient 0.998 and 0.991 respectively. For the area under curve the wavelength selected for quinine was from 227 nm to 237 nm and for ciprofloxacin 264 nm to 279 nm which gives peak area for quinine 0.370041 and for ciprofloxacin 3.60596. For the method C involved formation of isoabsorptive point at 246 nm.

INTRODUCTION

Quinine and ciprofloxacin are the drugs used in the treatment of malaria and typhoid fever respectively. Quinine is cinchona alkaloid that acts as a blood schizonticidal and weak gametocyte against *Plasmodium vivax* and *Plasmodium malariae*. As an alkaloid it is accumulated in the blood vacuoles of plasmodium species. Quinine is less effective and more toxic as a blood schizonticidal agent than chloroquine. However still it is very effective and widely used in the treatment of acute cases of severe *P. falciparum*. It is especially useful in the areas where there is known to be a high level of resistance to chloroquine. [1] Ciprofloxacin hydrochloride according to USP, a fluoroquinolone, is a monohydrochloride monohydrate salt of 1-cyclopropyl-6-fluoro-1,4-dihydro-4-oxo-7-(1-piperazinyl)-3-quinolinecarboxylic acid.

Ciprofloxacin has *in-vitro* activity against a wide range of gram-negative and gram-positive microorganisms. The bactericidal action of ciprofloxacin results from inhibition of the enzymes topoisomerase II (DNA gyrase) and topoisomerase IV, which are required for bacterial DNA replication, transcription, repair and recombination. [2-3]

Quinine sulphate is an antimalarial drug chemically described as cinchonane-9-ol, 6'-methoxy-(8 α , 9R)-sulphate (2:1) (salt), dihydrate with molecular formula of $(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and a molecular weight of 782.96. [4] Ciprofloxacin hydrochloride is an antibacterial drug and chemically described as 1-cyclopropyl-6-fluoro-1,4-dihydro-oxo-7-(1-piperazinyl)-3-quinolinecarboxylic acid hydrochloride monohydrate. Its molecular formula is $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{18}\text{FN}_3\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{HCl} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ with molecular weight 385.8. It is a pale yellow crystalline powder. [5]

There are so many methods described for the quinine and ciprofloxacin individually. However, there is no method reported for simultaneous estimation of both drugs.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

UV-visible double beam spectrophotometer Jasco model V-630 with spectral bandwidth of 2 nm, wavelength accuracy

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of ± 0.3 nm and a pair of 10 nm matched quartz cell was used. The API used as ciprofloxacin hydrochloride, quinine sulphate and the chemicals as distilled water was obtained from the institute P.D.V.V.P. College of Pharmacy, Ahmednagar.

Preparation of Stock Solution

Ciprofloxacin hydrochloride 10 mg was weighed by using electronic balance (Model Shimadzu AUW-220D) and dissolves in a small amount of distilled water and then completely dissolved. After this the solution was adjusted to 100 ml in volumetric flask, So that the solution of 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ was prepared. Like this the stock solution of quinine sulphate were also prepared by dissolving 10 mg of drug into distilled water. For complete solubility the solution was sonicated for 2 min by using ultrasonic bath sonicator (model 5.5L150H) and then adjusted the volume upto 100 ml in volumetric flask.

Preparation of Sample

From the stock solution of ciprofloxacin hydrochloride and quinine sulphate the standard solutions of both were prepared. For ciprofloxacin hydrochloride the standards were prepared as 5-35 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ by taking 0.5 ml of stock solution adjusted to 10 ml by using distilled water to prepare 5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 1 ml of stock solution was adjusted to 10 ml to get 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 1.5 ml of stock solution was adjusted to 10 ml to get 15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 2 ml of stock solution was adjusted to 10 ml to get 20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 2.5 ml of stock solution was adjusted to 10 ml to get 25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 3 ml of stock solution was adjusted to 10 ml to get 30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 3.5 ml was adjusted to 10 ml to get 35 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. After this the samples for quinine sulphate were prepared as 5-35 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The dilutions were prepared as 0.5 ml from stock were taken and diluted upto 10 ml so as to get the solution of 5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 1 ml stock solution were adjusted to 10 ml to get the solution of 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 1.5 ml stock solution were taken and adjusted to 10 ml to get 15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 2 ml of stock solution were taken and adjusted to 10 ml to get 20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 2.5 ml of stock solution were taken and adjusted to 10 ml to get 25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 3 ml of stock solution were taken and adjusted to 10 ml to get 30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 3.5 ml of stock solution were taken and adjusted to 10 ml to get 35 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

Figure 1: Structure of quinine sulphate

Figure 2: Structure of ciprofloxacin hydrochloride

Table 1: Optimized Method Parameters for Dual Wavelength Spectrophotometry

S. No.	Method Parameters	Optimized Parameters
1	Solvent	Distilled water
2	Scanning Range	200 nm to 400 nm
3	Scan Speed	Medium
4	Analytical wavelength for determination of quinine	233 nm and 272 nm
5	Analytical wavelength for determination of ciprofloxacin	233 nm and 272 nm

Table 2: Linearity

Quinine (Conc. µg/ml)	Absorbance		Ciprofloxacin (Conc. µg/ml)	Absorbance	
	233 nm	272 nm		233 nm	272 nm
5	0.4367	0.0594	5	0.1504	0.4145
10	0.7969	0.0870	10	0.3074	0.8675
15	1.1579	0.1237	15	0.5002	1.4166
20	1.5717	0.1667	20	0.6388	1.9152
25	1.9453	0.2086	25	0.8090	2.3762
30	2.2831	0.2411	30	0.9235	2.9328
35	2.7971	0.3305	35	1.0167	3.7255

Table 3: Intraday Precision Studies

S. No.	Concentration of Drug (µg/ml)	Absorbance Difference		SD Quinine	SD Ciprofloxacin	% RSD	
		Quinine	Ciprofloxacin			Quinine	Ciprofloxacin
1.	10 (n = 3)	0.8068	0.8575	0.005745	0.005716	0.7179	0.6640
		0.7969	0.8674				
		0.7968	0.8575				
2.	15 (n = 3)	1.1675	1.4265	0.005514	0.005774	0.4710	0.4057
		1.1770	1.4165				
		1.1674	1.4265				
3.	20 (n = 3)	1.5516	1.9151	0.005831	0.005662	0.3766	0.2961
		1.5415	1.9155				
		1.5516	1.9055				

Limit: % RSD for area NMT 2.0%

Measurement of Readings

After the sample preparation readings were taken by using Jasco make double beam UV visible spectrophotometer. For the measurement of samples the blank readings were taken for correction of baseline. For measurement of λ_{\max} 20 µg/ml samples of quinine sulphate and ciprofloxacin hydrochloride were taken. It shows the λ_{\max} of quinine sulphate and ciprofloxacin hydrochloride as 233 nm and 272 nm respectively. And the sample readings were taken by adjusting fixed wavelength at 233 nm and 272 nm.

Method A - Dual Wavelength Method

If a sample contains two absorbing drug of each of which absorbs at the λ_{\max} of the other, it may be possible to determine both drugs by the technique of simultaneous equations.

$$C_x = \frac{A_2 a_{y1} - A_1 a_{y2}}{a_{x2} a_{y1} - a_{x1} a_{y2}} \quad (1)$$

$$C_y = \frac{A_1 a_{x2} - A_2 a_{x1}}{a_{x2} a_{y1} - a_{x1} a_{y2}} \quad (2)$$

Method B - Area under Curve

For the simultaneous estimation using the area under curve method, suitable dilutions of the standard stock solutions (100 µg/ml) of quinine sulphate and ciprofloxacin hydrochloride were prepared separately in distilled water. The solutions of drugs were scanned in the range of 200-400 nm. For area under curve method, the sampling wavelength ranges selected for estimation of quinine sulphate and ciprofloxacin hydrochloride were 227-237 nm (λ_1 - λ_2) and 264-279 nm (λ_3 - λ_4). Mixed standards were prepared and their area under the curve was measured at the selected wavelength ranges.

Table 4: Interday Precision Studies

Day	Concentration of Drug ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance Difference		SD		%RSD	
		Quinine	Ciprofloxacin	Quinine	Ciprofloxacin	Quinine	Ciprofloxacin
1	10 (n = 3)	0.7969	0.8674	0.005744	0.005831	0.7238	0.3766
		0.7968	0.8573				
		0.7969	0.8674				
2	15 (n = 3)	1.1674	1.4265	0.005716	0.005947	0.4882	0.4179
		1.1773	1.4265				
		1.1674	1.4162				
3	20 (n = 3)	1.5516	1.9151	0.005831	0.005543	0.3766	0.2904
		1.5415	1.9055				
		1.5516	1.9055				

nit: % R.S.D. for area NMT 2.0%

Table 5: Limit of Detection and Limit of Quantification

Parameters	Quinine		Ciprofloxacin	
	At 233 nm	At 272 nm	At 233 nm	At 272 nm
LOD ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0.2430	0.2788	0.6287	0.1905
LOQ ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0.8448	0.7365	1.9053	0.5773

nit: % R.S.D. for area NMT 2.0%

Table 6: Regression Characteristics

Parameters	At 233 nm	At 272 nm
Beer's Law Range	5-30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	5-30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
Regression Equation ($y = mx + c$)	$y = 0.076x + 0.047$	$y = 0.103x - 0.089$
Slope (m)	0.07	0.103
Intercept (c)	0.047	-0.089
Correlation Coefficient (R^2)	$R^2 = 0.998$	$R^2 = 0.991$

Figure 3: Spectra of quinine sulphate in distilled water

Concentration of two drugs in mixed standard and the sample solution were calculated using equation (3) and equation (4).

$$C_x = \frac{A_2 a_{x2} - A_1 a_{y2}}{a_{x2} a_{y1} - a_{x1} a_{y2}} \quad (3)$$

$$C_y = \frac{A_2 - a_{x2} \times C_x}{a_{y2}} \quad (4)$$

Method C -Absorbance Ratio Method

Absorbance ratio method is the uses of absorbance at two selected wavelengths; one of them is isoabsorptive point and second is λ_{max} of any of the drugs. From the overlain spectra of the two drugs quinine sulphate and ciprofloxacin hydrochloride shows isoabsorptive point as 246 nm. The

second wavelength is 272 nm which is the λ_{max} of ciprofloxacin. Working standard solutions having the concentration range of 5-35 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ in distilled water. And the absorbance at isoabsorptive point and λ_{max} of ciprofloxacin were taken.

The concentrations of two drugs were measured by using the equations (5) and (6).

$$C_x = \left\{ \frac{(Q_m - Q_y)}{(Q_x - Q_y)} \right\} \times A_1 / a_{x1} \quad (5)$$

$$C_y = \left\{ \frac{(Q_m - Q_x)}{(Q_y - Q_x)} \right\} \times A_1 / a_{y1} \quad (6)$$

Where A_1 and A_2 are absorbance's of mixture at 246 nm and 272 nm, a_{x1} and a_{y1} are absorptivities of quinine and

Figure 4: Spectra of ciprofloxacin hydrochloride in distilled water

Figure 5: Overlain absorption spectra of quinine and ciprofloxacin showing isoabsorptive point (246 nm) in distilled water

Figure 6: Area under curve of quinine sulphate

ciprofloxacin at 272 nm, ax_2 and ay_2 are absorptivities of quinine and ciprofloxacin at 233 nm, $Q_m = A_2/A_1$, $Q_x = ax_2/ax_1$, $Q_y = ay_2/ay_1$.

Validation of Proposed Methods

The proposed methods were validated according to the International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) guidelines. [6]

1. Linearity

The calibration curves were taken for both quinine and ciprofloxacin at 233 nm and 272 nm. Both the drug shows linearity and obeys Beer's Law in the concentration range of 5-30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The correlation coefficient of calibration curves were 0.998 and 0.990.

2. Precision

Figure 7: Area under curve of ciprofloxacin hydrochloride

Figure 8: Standard calibration plot of quinine sulphate in distilled water

Figure 9: Standard calibration plot of ciprofloxacin hydrochloride in distilled water

Relative standard deviations (% R.S.D.) for intraday and inter day were calculated as precision study.

0.1905 for ciprofloxacin at the wavelength 233 nm and 272 nm.

3. Limit of Detection

The limit of detection was determined using the formula:

$$LOD = 3.3\sigma/S$$

Where, LOD is Limit of Detection, σ is the standard deviation, S is the slope of the calibration curve. [7] LOD was found to be 0.2430 and 0.2788 for quinine and 0.6287 and

4. Limit of Quantitation

The limit of quantitation was determined using the formula:

$$LOQ = 10 \sigma/S$$

Where, LOQ is Limit of Quantitation, σ is the standard deviation, S is the slope of the calibration curve. LOQ was

Table 7: Peak Areas of Quinine Sulphate and Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride by AUC

Area Under Curve for Quinine			
Peak	Wavelength Range	Area	Area Ratio
Peak 1	227-237	0.370041	1
Peak 2	227-237	0.370041	1
Area Under Curve for Ciprofloxacin			
Peak 1	264-279	3.60596	1
Peak 2	264-279	3.60596	1

found to be 0.8448 and 0.7365 for quinine and 1.9053 and 0.5773 for ciprofloxacin at the wavelength 233 nm and 272 nm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The combination of quinine and ciprofloxacin used to treat two diseases, the patient suffering simultaneously. The present work gives a very simple, accurate and economic method for the simultaneous estimation of both drugs. Both the drugs shows linearity at the wavelength selected 233 nm for quinine and 272 nm for ciprofloxacin and validated according to the ICH guidelines.

CONCLUSION

The new, simple, sensitive and economic UV spectroscopic methods were developed for the simultaneous analysis of ciprofloxacin and quinine.

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